

Case study of a harmful benthic event caused by *Gambierdiscus*

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Abstract

The increased numbers of adverse incidents associated with benthic harmful algae blooms (BHABs) has generated strong research interests in the last decade and calls for early warning system that provide warnings and reduce risk to human health. The complex habitats of BHABs make many detection methods difficult or unfeasible so case studies of bloom management, like the one we present here, are especially helpful.

Keywords: benthic harmful algal bloom, ciguatera, ciguatoxin, dinoflagellate, Early Warning System

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Introduction

Ciguatera poisoning (CP) has a long history with reports dating to the sixteenth century and affects 50,000 to 100,000 consumers of seafood annually. It is a poisoning caused by the ingestion of fish or shellfish from tropical and subtropical regions when lipid-soluble ciguatoxins (CTXs) produced by dinoflagellates of the benthic genera *Gambierdiscus* and *Fukuyoa* bioaccumulate in marine food webs. Renewed interest has spurred active research on these benthic organisms causing harmful blooms (BHABs) in the last two decades, producing much valuable information. However, there are some needs that require urgent attention (FAO and WHO, 2020). Sampling methods need to be standardized so cell abundances can be compared within and across regions. Too, there is a clear mandate for risk management plans to provide effective outreach programs and define protocols to avoid the risk of consuming tainted seafood. To provide sufficient lead-time for management activities an effective early warning system (EWS) must be in place.

Currently a Technical Guidance document for the Implementation of Early Warning Systems for Harmful Algal Blooms is being drafted jointly by the Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations (FAO), the International Oceanographic Commission of UNESCO (IOC-UNESCO) and the International Atomic Energy Agency (IAEA) for publication after pilot testing planned for 2022. Some of the most useful information in this document comes from case studies of harmful algal blooms (HABs) including the benthic ones (BHABs) like *Gambierdiscus* and *Fukuyoa*. Here we describe a case study

for *Gambierdiscus* and a nascent Early Warning System (EWS) for CP-causing dinoflagellates.

Ideally, an EWS should include the early detection of the presence of the harmful organism before it reaches threshold abundance values related to noxious impacts on the health of people (and/or the environment) and the determination of the involved toxic compounds specially in seafood. In regions with only sporadic BHAB events or areas without resources to test for toxins, EWS are generally based on detection of seasonal changes in cell abundances. Yet, Chinain *et al.* (1999) conducted a long-term survey in French Polynesia from February 1993 to December 1997 that included both *Gambierdiscus* cell abundances and toxicity and they concluded:

Toxicity screening revealed that toxin production was maximum from October 1994 through december 1996. No correlation was found between toxicity of these blooms and their biomass nor the seasonal pattern of temperatures. It has been suggested, that the toxicity of naturally-occurring blooms of *Gambierdiscus* spp. and, consequently, the severity of ciguatera incidents in a given area, is mainly dependent on the clonal nature of cells which coexist within local populations of this dinoflagellate.

Gambierdiscus and *Fukuyoa* cell abundances are not sufficient to support an EWS based on cell counts alone. Sampling the marine food web for CTXs is the most direct way to determine toxicity but it is both difficult and costly. To assist in sampling

environmental CTXs, passive sampling solid phase adsorption toxin tracking (SPATT) technology has been developed as a tool to monitor algal toxins (MacKenzie *et al.*, 2004; Roué *et al.*, 2018).

A number of *in vitro* and field studies have shown the use of the technique to trace an array of algal or cyanobacterial toxins in algal cultures or marine and coastal environments, including hydrophilic toxins such as saxitoxins and domoic acid, and lipophilic toxins, such as azaspiracids, brevetoxins, CTXs, okadaic acid and microcystins (Shea *et al.*, 2006; Stobo *et al.*, 2008; Fux *et al.*, 2009; Lane *et al.*, 2010; Kudela, 2011; Caillaud *et al.*, 2011). For example, Zendong *et al.* (2014) used passive samplers to capture toxins from both pelagic and benthic or epiphytic microalgae. Pinnatoxin-G and dinophysistoxin-1 were accumulated in significant amounts, indicating the presence of both *Vulcanodinium rugosum* and *Prorocentrum lima* in the study site.

Table 1. Species-specific relative cell abundance in three bays on Nuku Hiva Island in the Marquesas archipelago (French Polynesia), site of a ciguatera poisoning event in July 2014 that affected nine people who ate gastropods (*Tectus niloticus*) found to contain ciguatoxins. Data from Darius *et al.* (2018).

<i>Gambierdiscus</i> Species	Location		
	Anaho Bay	Taipivai	Taiohae
<i>G. caribaeus</i>	<1%	<1%	<1%
<i>G. carpenteri</i>	17%	90%	88%
<i>G. pacificus</i>	<1%	<1%	<1%
<i>G. polynesiensis</i>	82%	10%	10%
<i>G. toxicus</i>	<1%	<1%	<1%
Total cells	~2,900	~415	~420

Case study – Ciguatera Poisoning

EWSs based on field studies targeted at *Gambierdiscus* currently exist in several regions of the world. For example, the case study of Nuku Hiva Island in the Marquesas archipelago in French Polynesia is a good illustration of the benefits of an EWS approach that reduce the risk of exposure of local populations to ciguatera toxins in CP-prone areas.

In June 2014, a mass-poisoning outbreak involving nine tourists in Nuku Hiva Island following the consumption of a gastropod, *Tectus niloticus*, was reported in the frame of the country-wide epidemiological surveillance network established since 2007 in French Polynesia. All patients exhibited clinical symptoms typical of CP (Gatti *et al.*, 2018). The implication of this novel gastropod vector of high value for local populations in a CP incident prompted a two-years field survey involving the monitoring of *Gambierdiscus* species distribution and environmental toxins by means of passive samplers, the toxicity screening of *in vitro* cultures of *Gambierdiscus* spp. established from wild material, as well as a follow-up survey of the toxicity in *T. niloticus* specimens in three distinct fishing sites of Nuku Hiva Island, Anaho Bay, Taipivai Bay and Taiohae Bay.

The qPCR assays carried out on artificial substrate (window screen) devices (Tester *et al.*, 2014) to survey for *Gambierdiscus* relative cell abundance and species distribution showed a high species biodiversity in Nuku Hiva study site since up to five distinct species

were detected, with *G. polynesiensis* as the dominant species in Anaho Bay (~82%) vs *G. carpenteri* in Taipivai Bay and Taiohae Bay (90% and 88%, respectively) (Table 1).

The CBA-N2a and LC-MS/MS toxicity analyses conducted periodically on *T. niloticus* showed that only specimens collected from Anaho Bay were toxic (Fig. 1). Despite a progressive 19-fold decrease in CTX contents over time, the residual toxicity monitored in *T. niloticus* remained well above the safety limit recommended for human consumption even 28 months after the poisoning event (Fig. 1) (Darius *et al.*, 2018).

In parallel, several *Gambierdiscus* spp. cultures were also successfully established in the laboratory, although the culturing approach gave a highly biased representation of the community species composition in the three study sites as assessed by the artificial substrate method. It confirmed only one strain, a *G. polynesiensis* isolate, out of the 17 clonal strains examined produced CTXs at levels around 1.20 ± 0.14 pg P-CTX-3C equiv./cell. Conversely, none of the *G. carpenteri* isolates showed toxicity *in vitro*.

Fig. 1. Ciguatoxins in specimens of the gastropod *Tectus niloticus* sampled from Anaho Bay in Nuku Hiva Island (Marquesas, French Polynesia) over a 28-month period, as measured by a cell-based assay (CBA-N2a) and chemical analysis (LC-MS/MS). After Darius *et al.* (2018).

Based on LC-MS/MS data, four distinct P-CTX analogs were detected in toxic *T. niloticus* tissues, namely CTX3B, -3C, -4A and -4B, with CTX3B as the major congener. Since these four analogs are consistently found in *G. polynesiensis* culture extracts (Longo *et al.*, 2020), it can be concluded that *G. polynesiensis* populations, which predominate in Anaho Bay benthic assemblages, are the primary source of the CTX analogs detected in neighboring *T. niloticus*. Interestingly, these findings are consistent with the results of the field survey conducted in this same area by means of SPATT technology, which also showed evidence of the presence of CTX3B and -3C in the environment (Roué *et al.*, 2020). Of note, in addition to CTXs, okadaic acid and DTX-1 were also detected in SPATT extracts using a LC MS/MS-based multi toxin screening approach, thus, highlighting the usefulness of passive samplers in the routine surveillance of CP and other phycotoxin-related risks in ciguatera-prone regions.

Conclusions

Gambierdiscus live in complex benthic habitats and only rarely proliferate in the sense of a phytoplankton bloom, so an EWS based on remote-sensing information is not feasible. A combination of standardized sampling and species-specific cell identification of field samples, *in situ* toxicity monitoring using SPATT samplers and toxicity determination of wild samples/clonal cultures are necessary to fully understand the scope of a *Gambierdiscus* event that affects human health. Detailed case studies help guide future efforts to anticipate events in endemic CP areas and effectively mitigate CP events in new or unexpected places.

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References

- Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations and World Health Organization. (2020). Report of the expert meeting on ciguatera poisoning: Rome, 19-23 Nov. 2018. WHO. <https://apps.who.int/iris/handle/10665/332640>.
- Chinain, M., Germain, M., Deparis, X., Pauillac, S. *et al.*, (1999). *Mar. Biol.*, 135, 259-267.
- Caillaud, A., de la Iglesia, P., Barber, E., Eixarch, H., *et al.*, (2011). *Harmful Algae* 10, 433-446.
- Darius, H.T., Roué, M., Sibat, M. Viallon, J., *et al.*, (2018). *Tectus niloticus* (Tegulidae, Gastropod), as a novel vector of ciguatera poisoning. Detection of Pacific ciguatoxins in toxic samples from Nuku Hiva Island (French Polynesia). *Toxins* 10, 2.
- Fux, E., Bire, R., Hess, P. (2009). *Harmful Algae* 8, 523-537.
- Gatti, C.M., Lonati, D., Darius, H.T., Zancan, A., Roué, M., *et al.* (2018). *Toxins* 10, 102.
- Kudela, R.M. 2011. *Harmful Algae* 11, 117-125.

Lane, J.Q., Roddam, C.M., Langlois, G.W., Kudela, R.M. (2010). *Limnol. Oceanogr. Meth.* 8, 645-660.

Longo, S., Sibat, M., Darius, H.T., Hess, P. *et al.*, (2020). *Toxins* 12, 767.

MacKenzie, L., Beuzenberg, V., Holland, P., McNabb, P., *et al.*, (2004). *Toxicon* 44, 901-918.

Roué, M., Darius, H.T., Chinain, M. 2018. *Toxins* 10, 167.

Roué, M., Smith, K., Sibat, M., Viallon, J., *et al.*, (2020). *Toxins* 13, 321.

Shea, D., Tester, P., Cohen, J., Kibler, S., *et al.*, (2006). *Afr. J. Mar. Sci.* 28, 379-381.

Stobo, L.A., Lacaze, J.P.C.L., Scott, A.C., Petrie, J., *et al.*, (2008). *Toxicon* 51, 635-648.
Tester, P.A., Kibler, S.R., Holland, W.C., Usup, G., *et al.*, (2014). *Harmful Algae* 39, 8-25.

Zendong, Z., Herrenknecht, C., Abadie, E., Brissard, C., *et al.*, (2014). *Toxicon* 91, 57-68.

